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Open futures with E³UDRES² Ent-r-e-novators: Citizen Science, Research Excellence & Regional Impact

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We connect
various actors
and break down
barriers

Deliverable 4.1: Mapping Open Practices and Institutional Readiness

In this Newsletter edition we will focus on the Deliverable 4.1. “Report on the identified practices, barriers and needs for strengthening open research, open science and technology transfer between partners” results, which you can find on our [website](#). The Ent-r-e-novators WP4 team, developed a mixed method research that has combined surveys and interviews with quantitative and qualitative assessments of the level of awareness/engagement, acceptability and value perception with the main aim of understanding the current situation regarding Open Science, Open Innovation and Open Education policies in the partner institutions.

Open Education

Open Science

- Strengthening awareness and engagement

Open Education

- Limited policies and networking in place

Technology Transfer

- Combined surveys and assessments of practices and needs

Most of the partner institutions do not have policies or a defined strategy for Open Education, except for the University Politehnica of Timișoara, that is the only institution that has policies for Open Education

According to the responders, at the consortium level, there is limited networking among people in Open Education within institutions, as well as with external stakeholders. However, activities and actions for Open Education are developed for all the institutions.

In general, respondents are unaware of or consider the priority of incorporating Open Education in student theses to be low or very low.

Some of the main barriers preventing the incorporation of more open education resources into the curriculum identified in the consortium are: funding, lack of time, language, among many others. According to the responders, one of the best ways to give support in the Open Education area is to provide workshops training, and seminars on this topic. Regarding individual tools used for open education, at the Consortium level, the most commonly used tools are Moodle, followed by Kahoot, Canvas, and LibreOffice. Others like Inksape, Miro, H5P, and DaVinci Resolve, are either used or known by the researchers. At UPT besides a Moodle based platform called Virtual Campus, they also used the UPT’s MOOC platform called UniCampus.

To know more about these results, [follow the link to read the full deliverable 4.1](#).

Citizen Science: Driving Innovation with Real-World Impact

WP5 Results – Citizen Science and Engagement Competencies

Citizen science is revolutionizing the way universities collaborate with communities, businesses, and local governments to create meaningful, real-world impact. Within WP5 of the Ent-r-e-novators project, we have explored how researchers can enhance engagement in citizen science, ensuring that research is not only academically rigorous but also socially relevant and inclusive.

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Key Results & Outcomes

Through a multi-phased approach across six universities of applied sciences, we identified essential engagement competencies for researchers.

A **framework** was created, with **engagement strategies** divided in 8 categories to support researchers interested in engaging citizens and other stakeholders in their research. Based on this framework, we defined our **maturity model**, mapping engagement competencies based on the EURAXESS Researcher *Profile Descriptors*.

With this tool, one can scale his/her engagement skills ranging from junior to senior citizen scientist for these 8 categories. It gives a clear view of which skills you already possess, and which still need more development.

As Citizen science is meant to be transdisciplinary, everyone has their specific expertise. We don't expect one person to be an expert in all these skills. It's an interesting exercise to do this with a project team, to see if there are still gaps that need to be filled.

Furthermore, we developed **Interactive training tools**, including a gamified introduction to citizen science principles, a game to recognize different levels of engagement and a self-assessment game for engagement skills.

Citizen Science: results from WP5

Driving Innovation with Real-World Impact (cont.)

And lastly, we described insights of the role of **engagement angels** - regional facilitators and sponsors who sustain citizen participation in research and reported on the importance of **liminal spaces** (e.g., public spaces, campuses, hybrid venues) in fostering inclusive and diverse engagement.

Impact on E³UDRES² & Institutional Development

The Ent-r-e-novators project aligns with the E³UDRES² Alliance mission to scale citizen science from local to international collaborations. By integrating these insights, E³UDRES² fosters inter-regional knowledge-sharing, enabling successful citizen science initiatives to be adapted across diverse communities.

At the institutional level, our findings empower researchers with the skills and strategies needed to bridge the gap between academia and society. Strengthening citizen engagement not only enhances research quality but also builds trust, improves scientific literacy, and fosters sustainable innovation in local ecosystems.

By making science more inclusive, collaborative, and actionable, we are shaping the future of research—one that is deeply connected to the needs and aspirations of the communities we serve.

Discover how we're shaping the future of research; watch our latest insights and tools on [our YouTube channel](#).

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Connecting Science and Society: Ent-r-e-novators at the EXPER Final Conference

(E³UDRES² Ent-r-e-novators cluster project)

On March 10, 2025, the University of Las Palmas de Gran Canaria hosted the Final Conference of the EXPER Project, titled "Bridging Science and Society: The Future of European Research". The event marked the conclusion of 30 months of joint efforts to strengthen research excellence and institutional transformation in Europe's Outermost Regions, namely the Azores and the Canary Islands.

Funded by Horizon Europe, the EXPER project focused on capacity-building, talent retention, knowledge transfer, and the development of inclusive research ecosystems. The conference gathered representatives from the European Commission, researchers, policymakers, and innovation professionals to explore key challenges and opportunities facing Widening countries and regions.

As part of the programme, Luís Coelho, Associate Professor at the Polytechnic University of Setúbal and coordinator of the E³UDRES² Ent-r-e-novators project, took part in the session on "The Future of European University Alliances". His intervention presented the work developed under the Ent-r-e-novators initiative, including practices and tools that support research excellence and institutional collaboration.

This participation was a valuable opportunity to share project outcomes with a broader European audience, and to contribute to the reflection on how University Alliances can support innovation and transformation at regional and institutional level. By participating in this dialogue, Ent-r-e-novators helps inspire future collaborations and align with Horizon Europe's goals for openness, inclusion, and excellence in research.

Follow [this link](#) to learn more about the E³UDRES² Ent-r-e-novators cluster projects.

KU Leuven Open Science Day focuses on citizen engagement and researcher competencies

On May 6, 2025, KU Leuven hosted the annual Open Science Day, bringing together a diverse community of researchers, educators, and students committed to advancing transparency and collaboration in research. The event emphasised the growing relevance of citizen science as a transformative approach to research that empowers individuals, communities, and institutions to co-create knowledge and drive societal innovation.

A key highlight was the presentation of findings from the E³UDRES² Ent-r-e-novators project by researchers from University College Leuven Limburg (UCLL). Under the title Fostering Effective Citizen Science, the team explored how researchers can better engage the public through participatory methods. The study involved six universities of applied sciences and adopted a multi-phased methodology, including literature reviews, expert interviews, podcasts with citizen scientists, Delphi panels, and futuring workshops.

Empowerment Researcher profil
 Participatory methods Delphi panels Mapping
 Co-creation Open Science
Citizen science
 Co-creation Engagement
 Interactive tools
 Futuring works- Inclusive Open Science
 hops Engagement angels

The research resulted in the development of a maturity model outlining researcher engagement competencies, and a mapping tool allowing individuals to assess their readiness and areas for improvement. A board game was also designed to introduce key principles of citizen science in an interactive and accessible way.

In addition to these tools, the study emphasised the importance of liminal location spaces that blend formal and informal environments for collaboration and introduced the concept of engagement angels: local actors who serve as facilitators, motivators, or sponsors of citizen science efforts. These elements were identified as essential for creating inclusive, sustainable participation across different regional contexts. The Open Science Day reinforced the importance of equipping researchers with the tools and strategies needed to bridge the gap between academia and society, advancing one of Ent-r-e-novators' key missions.

Cybersecurity Meets Sustainability: A New Logistics Paradigm

On April 9, 2025, the **Logistics Day Conference – Cybersecurity and Sustainability in Supply Chains** took place at the **Szent István Campus of MATE in Hungary**. Organised as part of the **E³UDRES² Ent-r-e-novators project**, the event served as a dynamic forum for discussing two critical dimensions of modern logistics: the increasing relevance of cybersecurity and the urgent need for sustainability across supply chain systems.

With close to 100 participants, including over 30 on-site attendees and many more joining online, as well as a delegation from Hungary, the event brought together students, academic staff, and corporate professionals from across Europe. The programme was fully bilingual, promoting cross-border exchange of ideas and practices in line with Ent-r-e-novators' international scope.

Keynote speeches addressed challenges such as data protection in global trade flows, the vulnerability of digital infrastructure in logistics operations, and strategies for building resilience against cyber threats. In parallel, the sustainability track focused on green logistics, the reduction of environmental impact, and circular economy practices within the supply chain.

Speakers included experts from leading institutions and companies such as **Ernst & Young Hungary**, **Hungaro Gast**, the **University of Debrecen**, and the **Hungarian University of Public Administration and Service**, who shared cutting-edge insights and real-world case studies. The programme also featured a block dedicated to international student presentations, where young researchers had the opportunity to present findings and innovative ideas related to both cybersecurity and sustainability.

The Logistics Day Conference demonstrated how the combined focus on digital and ecological resilience can shape smarter supply chains for the future. It also highlighted the importance of collaborative education, practice-based learning, and institutional partnerships key pillars of the Ent-r-e-novators vision for Europe's innovation-driven higher education landscape.

Another milestone: IPS and UCLL receive the HR Excellence in Research Award

Funded by
the European Union

Another milestone: IPS and UCLL receive the HR Excellence in Research Award A shared achievement reflecting collaboration, strategic alignment and dedication to improving research environments

As part of the strategic goals of the E³UDRES² Ent-r-e-novators project, five of the six partner institutions applied for the **HR Excellence in Research (HRS4R)** Award — a European Commission distinction that recognises institutions aligning their HR policies with the principles of the European Charter for Researchers and the Code of Conduct for the Recruitment of Researchers.

Earlier this year, the Polytechnic University of Setúbal (IPS) was awarded the recognition, becoming the first Polytechnic Institution in Portugal to receive this honour. IPS joined St. Pölten University of Applied Sciences (STPUAS), which already held the distinction before the start of the Ent-r-e-novators project.

In July 2025, UC Leuven-Limburg (UCLL) also received the HRS4R award, becoming the third Ent-r-e-novators institution to secure this important recognition. UCLL has already begun sharing the news internally and externally, reinforcing its institutional commitment to improving research careers and support systems.

A coordinated European effort

All five partner institutions submitted their applications during the course of the project

HR EXCELLENCE IN RESEARCH

— a process that involved internal assessments, consultation with research staff, and the definition of action plans aligned with European standards.

This collective effort was carried out in record time and with strong institutional engagement.

The results so far are encouraging: by mid-2025, three Ent-r-e-novators partners — STPUAS, IPS, and UCLL — are officially recognised with the HR Excellence in Research label. The remaining two institutions are in the final stages of evaluation, with results expected soon.

Strategic relevance for Ent-r-e-novators

The HRS4R award directly contributes to one of the core objectives of the Ent-r-e-novators project: to create favourable condi-

tions for research excellence, career development and international attractiveness across the consortium.

The process:

- Reinforces transparent, open and inclusive recruitment practices;
- Strengthens institutional support for early-career researchers;
- Enhances the international positioning of each partner in the European Research Area

This recognition helps consolidate the Ent-r-e-novators ambition of supporting researchers and institutions in building smart and sustainable regions, grounded in high-quality, collaborative research ecosystems.

[More about HRS4R and the awarded institutions](#)

2 to 4 July 2025

Setúbal hosted the 2nd International Conference on Resilience and Sustainable Regions

From July 2 to 4, 2025, the Polytechnic University of Setúbal hosted the 2nd International Conference on Resilience and Sustainable Regions (ICRSR 2025).

Organised by the IPS Research Centre **RESILIENCE**, in collaboration with partners from the E³UDRES² alliance and other international institutions, the event aims to address key challenges shaping the future of regional sustainability.

Over three days, researchers, policymakers, community leaders, and multidisciplinary experts came together to explore innovative approaches to: territorial resilience, sustainability, artificial intelligence, collaborative tourism, sustainable bioeconomy, and Resilient governance.

The programme featured international keynote speakers, parallel scientific sessions, local best practice presentations, and spaces for networking and interdisciplinary dialogue, fostering impactful collaboration and knowledge exchange.

See the full programme here:
<https://icrsr.ips.pt/program/>

13 May 2025

Science Policy Conference

Shaping Policies, Inspiring Regions: Insights from the Science-Policy Conference

Last May, the E³UDRES² Ent-r-e-novators Science-Policy Conference took place at the Polytechnic University of Portalegre, Portugal, one day ahead of the EURASHE Annual Conference.

The event brought together researchers, policymakers, European Commission representatives, and members from various university alliances to reflect on how science and innovation can foster more sustainable and resilient regions.

The conference followed a single-track format, featuring sequential presentations from the Ent-r-e-novators work packages, along with contributions from related European projects and science-policy institutions.

Alongside the main sessions, **Thematic Corners** offered opportunities for networking and informal exchange, showcasing research centres and initiatives aligned with the Ent-r-e-novators mission.

Follow [this link](#) to learn more about the Conference and its shared materials.

13 MAY 2025

Science Policy Conference - Interactive Questions

As part of the Ent-r-e-novators Science Policy Conference, participants were invited to reflect on their own entrepreneurial mindset through a self-assessment question.

This question was shared via QR code and progressively introduced throughout the event, encouraging engagement and stimulating interest among attendees.

In addition, the audience was invited to respond to specific questions at the end of each of the four thematic sessions. Follow [this link](#) to explore the questions, answers, and overall conference results.

13 MAY 2025

Thematic Corners: MARE project

The Thematic Corners took place at the Science Policy Conference. The MARE Research Centre was represented by Luís Coelho, Coordinator of the Regional Research Unit MARE-IPS of the MARE Research Centre and associate professor at the Polytechnic University of Setúbal and Melanie Costa, representative of the MARE Research Centre.

During the Thematic Corners, MARE had the opportunity to discuss the MARE Research Centre, its composition, mission, and domains of research. They also shared their experiences and reflections on the project.

MARE has the technical and scientific skills to address all aquatic ecosystems, including river basins and adjacent areas, estuaries, coastal and oceanic marine ecosystems, MARE adopts an integrative and holistic approach, in close partnership with national and international institutions.

MARE is a multi-institutional centre, created in January 2015, with a nationwide territorial implantation.

It is located in eight Regional Research Units, at higher education campus in the Portuguese mainland, respectively University of Coimbra (MARE-UCoimbra), Polytechnic of Leiria (MARE-PLeiria), University of Lisbon (MARE-ULisboa), NOVA University of Lisbon (MARE-NOVA), ISPA (MARE-ISPA), Instituto Politécnico de Setúbal (MARE-IPSetúbal), University of Évora (MARE-UÉvora), and ARDITI/University of Madeira (MARE-Madeira).

MARE comprises more than 600 researchers, including 345 with PhDs. The MARE Research Centre videos on the Thematic Corners are available on our YouTube channel and also on our website.

Follow [this link](#) to learn more.

Luís Coelho

Melanie Costa

Open practices and international collaboration: A look back at the E³UDRES² Ent-r-e-novators PhD Summer School 2025

Open practices and international collaboration: a look back at the E³UDRES² Ent-r-e-novators PhD Summer School 2025. Between June 2nd and 6th, 2025, Timișoara (Romania) became the vibrant stage for the first edition of the E³UDRES² Ent-r-e-novators PhD Summer School, hosted by the Politehnica University of Timișoara. Themed around "Open Practices in Higher Education", this intensive five-day event brought together a dynamic community of over 70 in-person participants from 22 countries, as well as an additional 400 online attendees, united by a common purpose: shaping a more open, collaborative, and innovative academic future.

Organised as part of the European Universities Alliance E³UDRES² and driven by the Ent-r-e-novators project, the Summer School gathered 14 internationally recognised speakers from Romania, Portugal, Austria, Latvia, Hungary, Belgium, the Netherlands, and Italy. Experts led a diverse and immersive programme, combining morning lectures with afternoon hands-on activities, covering key topics such as: Open Education and Pedagogy; OER (Open Educational Resources) Production; Open Science and Open Access; Open Innovation and FAIR Data; Ethical Aspects in Open Research; AI in Open Learning Environments; MOOCs and Open Publishing.

This unique learning experience provided early-stage researchers with practical tools to implement Open Policies within their institutions, supported by real-world case studies, peer collaboration, and expert mentorship.

Beyond academia, the Summer School offered vibrant cultural activities, including a welcome dinner, a guided tour of Timișoara's historic centre, a visit to the National Museum of Banat, and a scenic Vaporetto boat cruise on the Bega River, which reinforced not only learning but also lasting international friendships.

As we reflect on the success of this inaugural edition, E³UDRES² reaffirms its commitment to empowering researchers through open, collaborative, and future-forward practices. The next generation of academic leaders is already shaping change, and it started here in Timișoara. For more details, [visit our website](#).

BETTER Life Bringing Excellence to Transformative Engaged Research in Life Sciences through Integrated Digital Centres

(E³UDRES² Ent-r-e-novators cluster project)

The BETTER Life project has made significant strides in promoting **Socially Engaged Research (SER)** within the life sciences, creating a rich ecosystem of frameworks, tools, digital resources, and training initiatives aimed at empowering early-career researchers (ECRs) and academic institutions. At the foundation of the project lies the developed Framework for **Socially Engaged Researchers in Life Sciences**, which offers a multi-stakeholder approach for fostering SER at the institutional, functional, stakeholder, and impact levels. It enables institutions to reflect on their internal capacities and processes while helping researchers understand the support structures and potential scientific, social, and economic impacts of their engagement. Additionally, both internal and external stakeholders can use the framework to assess how SER contributes to wider societal value.

Building on this foundation, the project introduced **Standards for Socially Engaged Research**, conceived as a flexible yet structured guide that evolves alongside the changing needs of life sciences and society. These standards form a stable “trunk” from which adaptable methodological “branches” can grow. They address essential questions of “what,” “who,” and “how,” providing clear directions and examples that help ECRs evaluate their strategies and align their work with broader societal concerns.

To operationalise the standards, the project developed **Toolkits for Socially Engaged Research**, each aligned with one or more of the twelve identified standards. These toolkits were designed as practical, adaptable resources shaped through collaborative workshops and stakeholder input. The result is a collection of ten templates that provide clear, actionable methods for conducting research that is socially relevant, responsive, and effective. These toolkits offer guidance on stakeholder engagement, evaluation, communication, and methodological design—empowering ECRs to embed social engagement deeply into their research practice.

The outputs of the project are made accessible through the **Digital Centre of Excellence (DCoE)** — an online platform serving as a hub for sharing project’s results and methodologies with the broader public, academic community, and quadruple helix stakeholders. The DCoE showcases toolkits, training materials, and other resources, ensuring their usability and accessibility while promoting the visibility of the project’s achievements across disciplines and institutions.

A major pillar of the project was **capacity-building and community engagement**, which were addressed through a robust series of training and experiential learning activities aimed at strengthening the capabilities of early-career researchers. The BETTER Life Virtual Spring School, held on April 9–10, 2024, introduced ECRs to the concept of socially engaged research and presented the tools and outcomes of the project. This online event focused on helping participants understand how to align scientific inquiry with real-world needs, using interactive lectures and group sessions. For its success, the second edition was launched in March 2025.

The project also organised a series of **Think Tank sessions** at each partner institution, bringing together experts to explore institutional needs and co-create tailored mentorship programs for ECRs. These think tanks played a key role in the development of institutional support systems, making sure that SER practices are embedded and sustained beyond the project's timeline.

Among the most intensive capacity-building actions were the **Virtual Boot Camps**, held in three progressive stages. *Boot Camp I* introduced foundational knowledge on the principles and relevance of SER. *Boot Camp II* focused on developing practical skills such as communication and stakeholder mapping. *Boot Camp III* emphasized building competencies in areas such as ethics, evaluation, and community collaboration. These Boot Camps provided not only structured training but also valuable networking and peer-to-peer learning opportunities, fostering a strong community of practice among ECRs.

The project culminated with the **BETTER Life Summer School**, a week-long in-person event that combined theoretical learning with practical fieldwork. Participants, including master's students, PhD candidates and postdocs, conducted field studies in two national parks in Czechia. Divided into small groups, they addressed local social, economic, and environmental challenges by engaging with stakeholders and applying the SER approach to real-world situations. Preparatory materials helped participants understand the context beforehand, and the fieldwork was complemented by discussions, presentations, and interactive workshops. The summer school not only deepened the participants' understanding of SER but also highlighted the tangible impact that life science research can have on communities.

Through these activities, the BETTER Life project has created a vibrant support system for socially engaged research in the life sciences. By integrating methodological tools, digital platforms, and dynamic training initiatives, it empowers ECRs to conduct impactful, responsible, and responsive research. The legacy of the project lies in its commitment to adaptability and collaboration, ensuring that the tools and structures developed will continue to evolve and inspire new approaches to integrating science with society.

[If you are interested in these areas, discover other Ent-r-e-novators cluster projects.](#)

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